

ANNOTATION GUIDELINE FOR FREE-TEXT ACTIVITY FUNCTIONING INFORMATION: INTERPERSONAL INTERACTIONS & RELATIONSHIPS

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1 INTRODUCTION

This work is a product of the Epidemiology and Biostatistics Section of the Rehabilitation Medicine Department, National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center that uses the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) (World Health Organization, 2001) as a framework to develop analytic tools for clinical natural language processing (cNLP) and to develop vocabularies of function. The interdisciplinary team is by design composed of a diverse set of scientists, including those in health informatics, mathematics, statistics, computer science, public health, and healthcare. The annotation team within the Section that created this guideline included clinical rehabilitation domain experts with backgrounds in occupational therapy, physical therapy, and primary care medicine, as well as individuals with public health and data science expertise.

Creation of the guideline was driven by a use case involving a collaborative agreement with the United States (U.S.) Social Security Administration (SSA) for leveraging cNLP to improve the disability determination process. The research purpose was to develop tools to automate extraction of relevant functional information from electronic health records (EHR) and support medical record review by adjudicators. This guideline aims to standardize interpersonal interactions and relationship information that is documented in free-text EHRs and provide a process for annotating this information. These efforts led to creation of a gold standard corpus, which has been used to develop computational models of functioning.

1.1 Use of this Guideline

We recommend that users of this guideline have a good understanding of Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships (IPIR) concepts and domain expertise, or access to persons with domain expertise, who can clarify concepts and their semantic representation for annotation in clinical documentation. Though the guideline was developed for manual annotation, it can also be used to develop automated annotation tools for those interested in standardizing the clinical documentation language of IPIR.

The guideline provides a review of the ICF and how functioning at the activity level is conceptualized and identified for annotation. Familiarity with the ICF and its coding scheme is essential. The ICF can be accessed through the [online ICF browser](#), which outlines ICF categories with code names and descriptions. ICF codes used in this guideline were those available on the ICF browser at the time the guidelines were developed. Users of the guideline need to be aware that the ICF is a working document with ongoing updates potentially adding new codes or modifications to code names and descriptions. Users are advised to check the ICF online browser for the most updated classification and codes.

Appendices are provided as an additional resource for users of the guideline. [Appendix 1](#) provides a full description of the ICF IPIR codes and definitions used in this guideline that were available at the time of annotation. [Appendix 2](#) shows a crosswalk done to link SSA criteria of mental functioning to related ICF b and d codes including the particular ICF codes used for IPIR annotations. [Appendix 3](#) provides a synthetic occupational therapy evaluation and discharge

note that has been annotated for IPIR information. [Appendix 4](#) lists abbreviations taken from the IPIR corpus used for annotation and includes additional common abbreviations found in clinical documentation.

Users of this guideline are expected to develop their own inter-rater reliability (IRR) measures among annotators and not benchmark their IRR on measures reported in this guideline.

1.2 Introduction to the ICF and conceptualization of function

The ICF was used as a framework to conceptualize functioning and standardize annotation of information at the activities level in EHR using clinical natural language processing (cNLP). The ICF was selected in view of its classification taxonomy of human functioning that has world-wide adoption and provides standardized language of functioning concepts with codes and operational definitions. Using the ICF to establish a common language for describing health and health-related states potential to improve communication between users, permit comparison of data across countries and disciplines, and provide a systematic coding scheme to be used by health information systems.

Functioning is classified on multiple levels from body structures (e.g., cellular, or organ, or organ system configurations); to body functions (e.g., mental functions); and functioning at the level of activities and participation of the person (e.g., self-care activities or work participation). An individual's functioning in a specific activity domain is understood as a complex relationship with dynamic interaction among a person's health condition, body structures and functions, and personal and environmental contextual factors (World Health Organization, 2001). Disability is understood as activity limitations or participation restrictions resulting from impairments and/or environmental barriers. See

Figure 1, the ICF scheme with the activity component highlighted, to show the focus of this work is on activity functioning.

Figure 1. ICF Framework with the Activity component highlighted

Functioning at the activity level is recognized as a salient healthcare outcome for both the individual and for population health (Bickenbach et al., 2023). Health is usually experienced by an individual as the ability to participate in activities that one wants, needs, or is expected to do. Electronic health records are a rich source of functioning information. Clinical NLP (cNLP) has helped to extract data on human functioning for use in research that can evaluate interventions and inform health care policy to benefit individual and population health (Hasan & Farri, 2019). These cNLP efforts, however, have focused primarily on body functions and structures for medical decision support such as diagnosing diseases and determining interventions (Bickenbach et al., 2023; Newman-Griffis et al., 2019). Extraction of functioning information at the activities level from the EHR is much less represented and challenging due to several factors including a lack of standardization of clinical documentation among providers and inconsistent representation across health systems (Newman-Griffis et al., 2019). As with all components in the ICF, the Activities and Participation component has several domains of functioning as can be seen in Figure 2 that highlights the interpersonal interactions and relationships (IPIR) domain.

The ICF uses an alphanumeric system of coding in which the letters b, s, d, and e are used to denote Body Functions, Body Structures, Activities and Participation, and Environmental Factors respectively. All codes in the Activities and Participation component of the ICF begin with a “d.” As IPIR is the seventh chapter, IPIR codes begin with “d7,” followed by numbers related to the sub-categories. These letters are followed by a numeric code that begins with the chapter number (one digit), followed by the second level (two digits), and the third and fourth levels (one digit each). Each functioning domain in the Activities and Participation component can be considered a parent category to subcategories nested within broader concepts. In the Activities and Participation component, codes can be added to denote qualifying constructs of capacity (the person’s ability to execute a task) and performance (the actual doing of the task). In addition, more than one code category can be applied to a particular function.

This guideline introduces annotation and coding of IPIR information at the activity level in support of cNLP efforts to automate information extraction in free-text EHR. ICF IPIR alphanumeric codes used for annotation of IPIR information were done at the second category level beginning with the chapter letter, followed by a 3-digit code (with the first digit representing the chapter number, and the next 2 digits representing the activity).

Figure 2. The Activities and Participation component of the ICF with the Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships domain highlighted

1.3 Conceptualizing Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships

The guiding framework of IPIR annotation is based upon concepts and terminology from three sources:

1. The ICF Activities and Participation Chapter 7 Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR)
2. The SSA Listings of Mental Disorders Paragraph B criteria of “Interact with others”
3. The SSA mental Residual Functional Capacity Assessment (mRFC) section C, Social Interaction.

The ICF IPIR domain consists of two major sections: (1) General interpersonal interactions, and (2) Particular interpersonal relationships, defined together as, “carrying out the actions and tasks required for basic and complex interactions with people (strangers, friends, relatives, family, intimate, and general others) in a contextually and socially appropriate manner” (ICF, 2001). See [Appendix 1: ICF Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships Codes and Definitions](#) as used in this guideline.

The SSA Listings of Mental Disorders Paragraph B criteria of Interact with others (paragraph B2) is defined as the area of mental functioning that “refers to the abilities to relate to and work with supervisors, co-workers, and the public. Examples include: cooperating with others; asking for help when needed; handling conflicts with others; stating own point of view; initiating or sustaining conversation; understanding and responding to social cues (physical, verbal, emotional); responding to requests, suggestions, criticism, correction, and challenges; and keeping social interactions free of excessive irritability, sensitivity, argumentativeness, or

suspiciousness” (Social Security Administration, 2023).

The SSA mental Residual Functional Capacity Assessment (mRFC) section C, Social Interaction is defined as “the ability to interact appropriately with the general public, to ask simple questions or request assistance, accept instructions and respond appropriately to criticism from supervisors, get along with coworkers or peers without distracting them or exhibiting behavioral extremes, maintain socially appropriate behavior and to adhere to basic standards of neatness and cleanliness” (Social Security Administration, 2024).

To conceptualize IPIR information for annotation purposes, a clear understanding of all aspects represented in this domain was needed. We approached this task by mapping IPIR language and concepts from the SSA references to codes from the ICF IPIR domain. See [Appendix 2](#) for a crosswalk of SSA criteria of mental functioning related to ICF b and d codes. This triangulation approach ensured all concepts related to functioning in IPIR were included for annotation. From the analysis of this information, we created an IPIR operational definition to guide development of the IPIR annotation schema and inform what information to include or exclude in the annotation of IPIR functioning information in clinical records.

IPIR is operationally defined as carrying out the actions and tasks required for basic and complex interactions with people (i.e., strangers, friends, co-workers, extended or immediate family members and romantic relationships and partners) in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.

The IPIR definition was further refined conceptually into four subcategories that include concepts from all three terminology sources: Interpersonal social skills; Interpersonal social interactions; Interpersonal communication; and Relationships. Interpersonal social skills are one’s personal skills and abilities needed to be able to interact appropriately. Interpersonal social interactions refer to the quality of interactions that occur within a social context. Interpersonal communication is the verbal and non-verbal communication that occurs within a social context. Relationships refers to the quality of particular types of relationships that people have in their lives with others, such as strangers, friends, relatives, family members, etc. These four IPIR subcategories were used for conceptualizing IPIR for annotation in the free text of health records.

2 ANNOTATION DATA

Data used for IPIR annotation came from two sources: clinical notes from the National Institutes of Health (NIH) Clinical Center and health records submitted to the Social Security Administration (SSA) by applicants for work disability benefits.

Health records within the NIH Clinical Center were provided by the NIH Biomedical Translational Research Information System (BTRIS), a resource available to the NIH intramural community, that provides records through limited data sets. The NIH Office of Human Subjects Research

Protection (OHRP) determined that research conducted with these limited data sets does not meet the definition of human subjects research pursuant to 45 CFR 46 and OHRP guidance.

The NIH dataset included 520 clinical notes from patients at the NIH Clinical Center. Domain experts iteratively filtered document types to narrow the dataset to documents containing information related to IPIR. The final subset consisted of 355 files corresponding to 25 Occupational Therapy (OT) discharge notes, 46 OT evaluation notes, 148 OT interim notes and 116 Social Work notes. (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Flowchart of NIH Clinical Center notes selected for annotation

A second dataset from SSA contained 2.5 million pages of medical evidence for which we developed a technique to draw samples for annotation that were more likely to contain IPIR information. Our domain experts created a list of IPIR-related key terms and short phrases that we then iteratively tested to define a page-level IPIR-relevance score used for weighted sampling, in combination with a measure of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) quality to exclude low quality pages. For any sampled page, one page before and after would be included if available and of sufficient OCR quality to provide additional context. Sampled document excerpts were between 1 and 3 pages long. This sampling technique was applied to create multiple samples of SSA excerpts for guideline development and IRR calculation.

Individual subsets of files from each dataset were used for the following purposes:

1. Create and test an operational definition for IPIR;
2. Establish acceptable Inter-Rater Reliability (IRR) between annotators;
3. Manual annotation of medical record files for IPIR information.

Testing the schema was an iterative process using a quality assurance procedure aimed at achieving satisfactory IRR, calculated as sentence-level Kappa score on the *ipir_yes* class between 2 annotators. Agreement was achieved with Kappa scores of 0.83 on the NIH dataset and 0.84

for the SSA dataset. With satisfactory IRR achieved, we identified a sample of 1,118 document excerpts for individual IPIR annotation (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Flowchart of SSA files selected for annotation

3 ANNOTATION TOOL

Following a comprehensive review of available annotation tools in 2017, we selected the General Architecture for Text Engineering (GATE) software tool (Cunningham et al., 2011) due to its ease of use, portability, and customizable features that met our needs for manual annotation and machine modeling. In addition, GATE did not require data to be on a repository outside the NIH firewall and did not have a cost associated with use. GATE is a general text processing framework that includes functionalities commonly found in typical NLP pipelines. While there are some disadvantages to this software, particularly related to co-reference annotation, its utilities were sufficient to satisfy the annotation needs and purpose in creating this guideline.

4 ANNOTATION SCHEMA

The IPIR annotation guideline and schema were developed through exploratory work by health professionals from multiple disciplines. We annotate IPIR information at the sentence level rather than the token (or word) level. Annotation therefore does not require manually selecting spans of tokens that contain functioning information. Instead, documents are prepared for annotation by running a sentence segmentation program, and during annotation, each sentence is labeled for the presence or absence of IPIR information.

There were multiple motivations for this approach. First, annotating precise token spans

requires boundary decisions that are difficult to prescribe in guidelines, which results in individual inconsistencies and variations between annotators that decrease IRR without reflecting true disagreement on the presence of functioning information. Second, annotating at the sentence level reduces annotation burden and results in higher annotation speeds. Finally, evaluation is simpler and more intuitive and different modeling architectures can be applied (i.e., sentence classification instead of named entity recognition).

The developed IPIR annotation schema (Figure 5) and workflow (Figure 6) reflect this sentence-level annotation strategy.

Figure 5. Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR) Classification Annotation Schema

4.1 Sentences, Attributes, and Values

An **IPIR sentence** is a sentence of type `ipir_yes`, which describes functional status information about the person’s basic and complex interpersonal interaction skills and the quality of a particular types of interpersonal relationships the person engages in.

All sentences can receive IPIR **Attributes** and **Values**. All values are binary (`true` or `false`). Attributes describe difficulty to determine IPIR presence (`difficult_to_determine` attribute), and presence/absence of ICF code classes from the two major sections of ICF IPIR codes: General interpersonal interactions, and particular interpersonal relationships. The IPIR classification schema separately classifies (1) basic and complex interpersonal interactions, using the ICF code range d710-d729, and (2) particular interpersonal relationships, using specific codes within the d730-d779 range.

Figure 6. Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR) Annotation Workflow

4.2 Detection of IPIR information

The IPIR annotation schema has two sentence-level annotation types: *ipir_yes* if IPIR information is present in the sentence and *ipir_no* otherwise. As part of the document preprocessing for annotation, all sentences were labeled as type *ipir_no* by default. Manual annotation then involved changing the type of the annotated sentence to *ipir_yes* if the sentence contained IPIR information. If an IPIR sentence was segmented into two or more pre-annotated sentences, all sentences were annotated if they contained IPIR information.

Difficult to determine attribute

All sentences (of types *ipir_yes* and *ipir_no*) have a *difficult_to_determine* attribute. This attribute was created to codify those areas where an annotator has to expend more than usual cognitive effort to make a determination about IPIR presence, along with cases where there is some uncertainty to the validity of the annotation. This information is thought to be useful to instruct the model to either learn from or exclude difficult cases. We expand this to include sentences to be marked as difficult to determine that the annotator thinks would be difficult to determine without context that is either hidden, scoped beyond a local

window, the context is blatantly inferred, or situations where the intent is clear even if there are spelling errors, formatting issues where non-relevant text is injected between what, in the original form would have made sense. The *difficult_to_determine* attribute is set to the *false* value by default.

4.3 Classification of IPIR information

The ICF chapter d7 Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships has two major code sections: general interpersonal interactions, and particular interpersonal relationships. The IPIR annotation schema separately classifies (1) basic and complex interpersonal interactions corresponding to the ICF code range d710-d729, which we label simply as Interaction, and (2) particular interpersonal relationships corresponding to codes in the d730-d779 range, which we describe below. Each *ipir_yes* sentence must receive at least 1 *true* annotation in the particular interpersonal relationships code range. Sentences of type *ipir_no* receive no ICF code classification annotations.

After identifying a sentence as containing IPIR information (*ipir_yes*), ICF IPIR codes are assigned at the sentence level. If multiple IPIR concepts are present in a single IPIR sentence, or if multiple ICF codes correspond to a single IPIR concept, all relevant ICF codes are assigned at the sentence level.

General interpersonal interactions attribute

General interpersonal interactions include basic and complex interactions. Basic interpersonal interactions (ICF code d710) are defined as “interacting with people in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by showing consideration and esteem when appropriate, or responding to the feelings of others” (World Health Organization, 2001, p. 159). Complex interpersonal interactions (ICF code d720) are defined as “maintaining and managing interactions with other people, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by regulating emotions and impulses, controlling verbal and physical aggression, acting independently in social interactions, and acting in accordance with social rules and conventions, when for example playing, studying or working with others” (World Health Organization, 2001, p. 160).

For annotation purposes, we do not distinguish between d710 Basic interpersonal interactions and d720 Complex interpersonal interactions for two reasons:

- Distinguishing between the two categories is difficult, partially because d720 assumes d710 and it likely would be too difficult to achieve satisfactory IRR on this distinction.
- None of our target use cases required separating d710 from d720. That is, in practice, these codes would be combined for display.

Since basic and complex interpersonal interaction concepts are combined, annotators do not have to choose between one or the other. If an IPIR sentence contains evidence of a person’s interpersonal interaction skills and abilities, it is annotated with the *interaction* attribute that represents the ICF code range of d710-d729.

Particular Interpersonal Relationships attributes

Relationships described in an IPIR sentence can be coded with one or more codes from the particular interpersonal relationship d730-d779 ICF code range. If no relationship is described or the type of relationship cannot be inferred from the sentence, no relationship code is annotated. Relationship ICF codes used for annotation are:

- d730 Relating with strangers
- d740 Formal relationships
 - d7400 Relating with persons in authority
- d750 Informal social relationships
- d760 Family relationships
- d770 Intimate relationships
- d779 Particular interpersonal relationships, other specified and unspecified

Code d7400 Relating with persons in authority is annotated when it applies. This code can only be annotated if d740 is also applied since it is more specific. This 4-digit code is included in annotation as it is of particular interest to SSA and adding it did not change the underlying classification structure.

5 GENERAL CONSIDERATIONS

5.1 General Guidelines for Annotating IPIR Sentences

1. Do not annotate IPIR language that does not directly or specifically indicate functional information about a patient. For example, IPIR language seen in instruction sheets to providers, or cover letters, are not annotated.
2. Many IPIR sentences will have information about interactions of others toward the patient. Only IPIR interaction information about the patient is annotated. For example, “Member reports when she was younger her mother was strict and would often put her down” would be annotated as d760 as shows the quality of the relationship between the patient and mother. Interactions here are referring to the mother’s quality of interaction, not the patient’s, therefore interaction is not annotated.

5.2 Annotate for semantics and not syntax

At times, clinical documentation of IPIR information can be challenging due to subtle differences in meanings. Sentences containing IPIR information are always annotated for their meaning and not their syntax. For example, “The patient shared a recent stressful interaction that he had with a woman at a restaurant” would only be coded as a relationship with a stranger d730. Feelings of an interaction do not give information about the actual interaction itself or the interaction skills demonstrated. Only the quality of relationship with strangers is annotated.

5.3 Grammatical and typographical errors

Grammatical and typographical errors do occur in clinical documents. When annotating, do not

edit the text of the record. If the annotator can understand the text as written and it contains IPIR information, then it should be annotated.

5.4 Annotate negation of IPIR information

Negation related to IPIR such as social skills that a person does not have, or social relational behaviors that a person does not do is annotated. For example, “Patient has no difficulty discussing fears/concerns about pain with the medical team” or “There is no implied or overt anger or hostility” would be annotated.

5.5 Annotation of Goals and Recommendations

Goals and recommendations related to IPIR are annotated only if they are met or partially met as this indicates the patient completed or partially completed the IPIR-related activities or behaviors.

Example 1: Would continue to benefit from discussion group to share lifeline activity and provide feedback to peers. Goal met

Example 2: Short term goal: Attend next OT Cooking Group session and participate in at least 2 meal preparation tasks with set-up and general supervision in order to engage in an essential daily living activity in preparation for returning to supported living in the community. Partially met. Patient was able to complete tasks with general supervision during the last 2 sessions.

5.6 Future statements

In IPIR annotation there are no attributes for past or present but IPIR information for past and future is annotated if IPIR functioning information is described. For example, “He has family/friends that will help him after discharge” shows there is already a relationship present that extends into the future. However future IPIR information that is uncertain is not annotated. For example, phrases like “may attend the group” would not be annotated.

Past IPIR information, including childhood, such as “She did not play with toys or with other children” or “She would scream when strangers to her, but known to her parents, entered the house” is annotated.

5.7 Hypothetical statements

Do not annotate IPIR-related hypothetical statements, including if, wish, want, could, would, etc. For example, “Patient believes in God and did indicate that daily interaction with a chaplain while here, daily, would be supportive” would not be annotated.

An exception is wanting a relationship with others outside of familial relationships, such as friends. A desire or want to have friends or to date is a first step toward forming a relationship. For example, “He wants to have friends” would be annotated.

5.8 Annotating Test scores

Test scores that only measure IPIR are annotated. Composite scores that contain IPIR information exclusively are annotated. Composite scores containing domain information outside of IPIR are not annotated. Standard scores of IPIR information, including range, are annotated. Percentiles are not annotated. IPIR test scores may consist of multiple sentence segments; each segment is coded with the same Relationship and Interaction code with the *difficult_to_determine* attribute coded as *false*. See examples below where different color highlights depict sentence segments.

In the following example, each sentence segment under Domain and Standard Score are annotated the same way [relationship = d799] [interaction = true] [difficult_to_determine = false]. The percentile is not annotated.

DOMAIN	Standard Score	Percentile
Socialization	35 +/- 9	<0.1

In the example below, only the score corresponding to IPIR information is annotated. An IPIR category missing a score is not annotated. As the composite score contains domains outside of IPIR it is excluded from annotation.

RTFA Coping Skills:	4
RTFA Leisure Skills:	8
RTFA Group Interaction Skills:	
RTFA Social Appropriateness:	4
RTFA Total Rating (MAX 20):	16

6 SPECIFIC CONSIDERATIONS FOR IPIR

IPIR sentences can be coded in one of two ways: (1) only for relationships, or (2) for both interaction and relationships. A Relationship code is a mandatory code for Interaction to be coded. Interaction is never coded on its own without a relationship qualifier as all interactions are assumed to be with others. These concepts are defined and operationalized for annotation with examples in the next section.

6.1 Distinguishing between Interactions and Relationships

To distinguish between interactions and relationship information, the quality of each is an important identifier for annotation.

What are Qualities of Interactions?

Interactions are a *demonstration or behaviors of the interaction skills* someone has – such as being cooperative, acting aggressively toward others, etc. As a general rule – interactions are behaviors one does in a social context that reflects one’s social and interaction skills. The *quality* of a person’s interaction skills would be things such as demonstrating warmth, respect, self-regulation of one’s anger, etc. during interaction with others. For annotation

purposes descriptions by providers of the *quality* of a person’s appearance (hygiene, grooming, clothing) during the interview or session is captured due to the relevance of how one is perceived by others in a social context. Participation within a social context also implies interaction, such as participated in therapy or in a group. Sentences with the term of interacts, or getting along is considered interaction information.

What are Qualities of Relationships?

As a general rule, a quality *gives a sense of the relationship* – such as conflict, stress, harmony, closeness – without any specifics of interactions that are currently occurring in that relationship. Feelings are indicative of a relationship quality such as *feelings* the person has about a relationship or relationships, i.e., feelings of letting the family down, feeling angry toward a specific person, feeling uncomfortable around others, etc. Intentionally spending time with others such as visiting, is annotated as a quality to a relationship since it is an indicator that a relationship is being maintained.

6.2 General Interpersonal Interactions

The ICF general interpersonal interactions is made up of both basic and complex interactions. Basic interpersonal interactions (ICF code d710) are defined as, “Interacting with people in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by showing consideration and esteem when appropriate, or responding to the feelings of others” (ICF, 2001 p.159). Complex interpersonal interactions (ICF code d720) are defined as, “Maintaining and managing interactions with other people, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by regulating emotions and impulses, controlling verbal and physical aggression, acting independently in social interactions, and acting in accordance with social rules and conventions, when for example playing, studying or working with others” (ICF, 2001 p. 160).

Table 1 lists all ICF Interaction codes, with their description and conceptual operational definition. Parent 3-digit ICF codes are bolded, with child 4-digit codes not bolded. Please see Section 7 in this document for text examples and coding of Interactions.

Table 1. ICF Interaction codes and operationalization

ICF code and name	ICF code description	Operational application
d710 Basic interpersonal interactions	Interacting with people in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by showing consideration and esteem when appropriate, or responding to the feelings of others.	The quality indicator of an interaction. These are descriptions of behaviors that provide information of a person’s interactions skills.
d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships	Showing and responding to consideration and esteem, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.	May be demonstrated such not interrupting and listening in conversation, references to getting along with someone, etc.
d7101 Appreciation in relationships	Showing and responding to satisfaction and gratitude, in a	May be demonstrated by thanking a therapist for their

	contextually and socially appropriate manner.	help or refusing to accept help from another.
d7102 Tolerance in relationships	Showing and responding to understanding and acceptance of behavior, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.	Demonstrated by putting up with behaviors from others, such as a wife putting up with a husband's grumpiness, etc.
d7103 Criticism in relationships	Providing and responding to implicit and explicit differences of opinion or disagreement, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.	Demonstrated by descriptions of tactful communication skills during more difficult interactions between people, such as responding to a supervisor's correction in a work setting.
d7104 Social cues in relationships	Giving and reacting appropriately to signs and hints that occur in social interactions.	These are any cues that are perceived visually without any touch or physical contact – such as eye contact during interactions, smiling, frowning, etc.
d7105 Physical contact in relationships	Making and responding to bodily contact with others, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.	These are cues given or perceived through direct touching of any intensity, such as hugs, pushing, stroking etc.
d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons	Showing differential responses to individuals, such as by reaching out for the familiar person and differentiating them from strangers and reacting in an appropriate manner.	Can apply to persons with developmental and/or cognitive issues such as memory loss and involves ability to recognize familiar people from strangers.
d720 Complex interpersonal interactions	Maintaining and managing interactions with other people, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by regulating emotions and impulses, controlling verbal and physical aggression, acting independently in social interactions, and acting in accordance with social rules and conventions, when for example playing, studying or working with others.	These are descriptions of <i>behaviors</i> that provide information of a person's interactions skills. This includes responding to humor, which also has a cultural component. Information such as "gets along", "relates well" or their negation is annotated as interaction.
d7200 Forming relationships	Beginning and maintaining interactions with others for a short or long period of time, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by introducing oneself, finding and	Behaviors one does when interacting with persons they have just met for the first time

	establishing friendships and professional relationships, starting a relationship that may become permanent, romantic or intimate.	
d7201 Terminating relationships	Bringing interactions to a close in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by ending temporary relationships at the end of a visit, ending long-term relationships with friends when moving to a new town or ending relationships with work colleagues, professional colleagues and service providers, and ending romantic or intimate relationships.	Behaviors referring to interpersonal skills of bringing a relationship to a close in an appropriate manner to person and context.
d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions	Regulating emotions and impulses, verbal aggression and physical aggression in interactions with others, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.	Self-regulating emotions and strong feelings so interactions with others remains respectful.
d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Acting independently in social interactions and complying with social conventions governing one's role, position or other social status in interactions with others.	Descriptions of interactions with others that are within one's social roles, mores and culture and expected by others.
d7204 Maintaining social space	Being aware of and maintaining a distance between oneself and others that is contextually, socially and culturally appropriate.	Descriptions of behaviors indicative of an understanding of social space such as standing too close to someone.
d729 General interpersonal interactions, other specified and unspecified	This category is an 'unspecified' residual category	These include IPIR information that may not fit within any of the above codes but <i>have implications for interactions</i> and include mRFC policy such as provider observations and documentation of a person's appearance appropriate to context.

6.2.1 Special considerations for Interactions

Eye contact

Eye contact during interpersonal interactions may be influenced by cultural norms, disposition such as shyness, or symptoms of a condition such as autism. Eye contact is IPIR information when it is described in the context of a social interaction and has a qualifier such as good, poor, or appropriate. Eye contact in IPIR refers to the visual social cues and aligns with ICF d7104 Social cues in relationships, defined as giving and reacting appropriately to signs and hints that occur in social interactions.

6.3 Particular Interpersonal Relationships

This section is about particular types of relationships people have in their lives, from short and temporary relationships with strangers, to relationships that are created and maintained over a longer time. **Feelings, wants, desires**, or lack thereof, toward others can potentially impact the creation and maintenance of relationships and is information an adjudicator could find useful. These include the emotional component, such as comfort level of being around other people (crowds, etc.), one’s attitude toward others, one’s satisfaction or dissatisfaction in a relationship, liking or not liking someone, closeness or estrangement in a relationship, etc. The following are examples of sentences that include relationship information, without any interaction information, that illustrate feelings, wants, interests, desires:

- He feels detached from others [d779 others]
- She likes to do things for others [d779 others]
- She wants to have friends [d750 informal]
- He is not interested to begin dating again [d770 intimate]

Beliefs, thoughts, and attitudes toward others provide information about the quality of a relationship and is annotated. The reason certain thoughts occur is not of interest. The interest is in the thoughts or beliefs that exist and can impact the quality of the relationship. For example, “he believes his father is trying to poison him” provides information about the quality of that relationship and is annotated, regardless of the “why”, such as paranoia stemming from a psychiatric condition.

For annotation, each particular ICF relationship code is assigned to an IPIR sentence only if information about a particular relationship exists. To assist annotator decision-making the following Table 2 describes each particular ICF relationship code and its subclassifications in order to operationalize how relationship codes are assigned for either a confirmation or a negation of presence of relationship information. Only the bolded codes are in the IPIR schema for annotation, though all codes in this domain are shown to assist an annotator in decision-making. Three-digit parent codes are justified to the left, with 4-digit child codes indented.

Table 2. ICF Particular Relationship codes and operationalization

ICF code and name	ICF code description	Operational application
d730 Relating with strangers	Engaging in temporary contacts and links with strangers for specific purposes, such as asking for directions or making a purchase. Engaging in temporary contacts and links with strangers for specific purposes, such as when asking for information, directions or making a purchase.	Applies to persons one interacts with for a short and temporary time. This could include temporary relationships such as someone who works with the public, or deals with a public servant, a fellow passenger, a store clerk, etc. Public is operationalized to mean pertaining to people as a whole, or dealing with a community of

		people at which a particular activity aims, such as working with the public, relating to the public etc. (Merriam- Webster dictionary, 2023)
d740 Formal relationships	Creating and maintaining specific relationships in formal settings, such as with teachers, employers, professionals or service providers.	Operationalized as including information relating to two specific ICF formal relationship sub-codes: d7401 Relating with subordinates and d7402 Relating with equals (see below). Health care providers included.
d7400 Relating with persons in authority	Creating and maintaining formal relations with people in positions of power of a higher rank or prestige relative to one's own position, such as an employer.	Code as both d740 and d7400. Operationalized as an employer, supervisor, public authority figures such as the police. This 4-digit child code is assigned in the IPIR schema.
d7401 Relating with subordinates	Creating and maintaining formal relations with people in positions of lower rank or prestige relative to one's own social position, such as an employee or servant.	Code d740. Operationalized as persons one could be supervising in an ongoing relationship such as a housekeeper, paid assistant caregiver or home help.
d7402 Relating with equals	Creating and maintaining formal relations with people in the same position of authority, rank or prestige relative to one's own social position.	Code d740. Co-workers are considered equals, unless otherwise stated in the context (such as "went out to lunch with a co-worker" where this would be coded d750 informal)
d750 Informal social relationships	Entering into relationships with others, such as casual relationships with people living in the same community or residence, or with co-workers, students, playmates, people with similar backgrounds or professions.	Informal relationships also include "ex" such as ex-wife, ex-boyfriend that someone still knows. Co-workers are included in this code.
d7500 Informal relationships with friends	Creating and maintaining friendship relationships that are characterized by mutual esteem and common interests.	Code d750. Operationalized wanting or desiring to make friends and having a friend. Friends are special relationships as they take effort. Visiting or living close to a friend also shows a relationship is present.
d7501 Informal relationships with neighbors	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people who live in nearby dwellings or living areas.	Code d750. Neighbors can be friends also.

d7502 Informal relationships with acquaintances	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people whom one knows but who are not close friends.	Code d750
d7503 Informal relationships with co-inhabitants	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people who are co-inhabitants of a house or other dwelling, privately or publicly run, for any purpose.	Code d750. Can include roommates.
d7504 Informal relationships with peers	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people who share the same age, interest or other common feature.	Code d750. Includes therapeutic and other peer support groups such as AA, cooking groups, etc. where there is a common interest or purpose among members. Church groups included.
d760 Family relationships	Creating and maintaining kinship relationships, such as those with members of the nuclear family, extended family, foster and adopted family and step-relationships, more distant relationships such as second cousins, or legal guardians.	Family relationships can be created, maintained but also terminated. All types of contact, or lack of contact are annotated.
d7600 Parent-child relationships	Becoming and being a parent, both natural and adoptive, such as by having a child and relating to it as a parent or creating and maintaining a parental relationship with an adoptive child, and providing physical, intellectual and emotional nurture to one's natural or adoptive child.	Code d760. Creating and maintaining a relationship with one's adoptive or biological child, no matter the child's age.
d7601 Child-parent relationships	Creating and maintaining relationships with one's parent, such as a young child obeying his or her parents or an adult child taking care of his or her elderly parents.	Code d760. Creating and maintaining a relationship with a parent, such as visiting a parent or having no contact with the parent.
d7602 Sibling relationships	Creating and maintaining a brotherly or sisterly relationship with a person who shares one or both parents by birth, adoption or marriage.	Code d760. Creating and maintaining a relationship with a sibling, such calling a sister or having no contact with a brother.
d7603 Extended family relationships	Creating and maintaining a family relationship with members of one's extended family, such as with cousins, aunts and uncles and grandparents.	Code d760. Creating and maintaining a relationship with an extended family member, such support from an uncle or breaking all contact with a cousin.
d770 Intimate relationships	Creating and maintaining close or romantic relationships between	Includes domestic partners, life partners, significant others, etc.

	individuals, such as husband and wife, lovers or sexual partners.	Evidence of a sexual relationship is not necessary for an intimate relationship code to be assigned.
d7700 Romantic relationships	Creating and maintaining a relationship based on emotional and physical attraction, potentially leading to long-term intimate relationships.	Code d770. Includes girlfriend/boyfriend, or fiancé. Includes wanting or desiring (or not) to date and dating. Includes breaking up information.
d7701 Spousal relationships	Creating and maintaining an intimate relationship of a legal nature with another person, such as in a legal marriage, including becoming and being a legally married wife or husband or an unmarried spouse.	Code d770. Operationalized as wife, husband or partner. The time in a relationship such as how many years of marriage is included as it may indicate a quality to the relationship. Annotate relationship status such as married, divorced, separated. Do not include status with deceased person such as “widow”.
d7702 Sexual relationships	Creating and maintaining a relationship of a sexual nature, with a spouse or other partner.	Code d770. Sexual intimacy is annotated. Body functions of sexual function or dysfunction is not annotated unless it relates to how the relationship is affected.
d779 Particular interpersonal relationships, other specified and unspecified	This category is an 'unspecified' residual category	Operationalized as general relationships where no particular relationship can be specified such as “others”, “other people”, “crowds”, “someone”, etc. Any general reference to social isolation/withdrawal, etc. is annotated as a relationship as it implies a social relationship (or lack thereof) linked to creating and maintaining relations with others. Crowds are operationalized as a large number of people who gather together in close spatial proximity with a common short or long-term purpose (Sociology Group, 2023). General social information such as reference to support networks, social support with unspecified others is coded d779 with no interaction.

6.3.1 Special considerations of relationships

Context Informs Relationships

Sometimes in an IPIR sentence, the relationship is not specified. However, the context provides information of the relationship type in that sentence. In that case, do take the contextual information and code the relationship accordingly. Many notes imply interactions with the provider who wrote the note. If one could add “with this provider”, or equivalent, at the end of the sentence, code for the formal relationship that the interaction occurs in. For example, “behavior was appropriate, cooperative, pleasant” is within the context of the formal interaction with a provider (i.e., “behavior was cooperative” [with this provider]); Code d740 formal relationship. A sentence such as “was responsive to humor” denotes interactions that could be in the context of an informal group or individually with another person or provider. Though the sentence alone does not specify any particular relationship, the context around the sentence may provide relationship information (possibilities include d750 informal or d740 formal etc.). “Withdrawn” is another context-specific social relationship, coded as d779 when it is a general statement applied to generalized others, or coded more specifically if it is behavior within an interview with examiner d740 or in a group d750.

A relationship can sometimes fall within more than one code. In these cases, context will inform how to code. Co-workers can be coded as either d740 formal relationship or d750 informal relationship and is dependent on the context. For example, “gets along well with co-workers” indicates a formal relationship and coded d740. A sentence such as “he feels supported by his friends and his co-workers who were very understanding” indicates coworkers are more of an informal relationship d750. In another example, “she confided in someone at work” could be both a supervisor (formal relationship) and/or a friend (informal relationship). In this case however, “someone” is general and would be coded as d779 other unspecified.

Sometimes settings are referred to with the implications of relationships. For example, “He is uncomfortable in a crowded setting” means uncomfortable in crowds and annotated as a quality to an unspecified relationship d779. A work setting can be implied, such as “she relates well at work”. Since no particular relationship is specified, d779 is coded for unspecified others.

Groups

Groups are often used in behavioral health and can include support groups (such as alcoholics anonymous) and other therapeutic groups (such as an occupational therapy cooking group), or community groups (such as religious groups). Groups often consist of a facilitator who may be a health provider and group members who are usually peers or persons with similar or common interest or features. A group is coded as formal or informal depending on the interaction and relationship described. For example, descriptions of participation in a support or therapeutic group or group activity, is coded as interaction d750 within an informal relationship. Responding directly to a group facilitator, such as a therapist, is coded as d740 an interaction within a formal relationship.

Primer for creating a relationship

Creating a relationship outside of family implies more effort is needed on the part of the person to initiate the formation of those non-family relationships. Therefore, we include annotation information about desires or no desires to have friends or date since that takes effort and is considered a primer or first step in creating a relationship. As stated earlier, one’s feelings, thoughts, wants, desires, or lack thereof, toward others can potentially impact the creation and maintenance of relationships. These include the emotional component, such as comfort level of being around other people (crowds, etc.), one’s attitude toward others, one’s satisfaction or dissatisfaction in a relationship, liking or not liking someone, closeness or estrangement in a relationship, etc. Table 3 provides text examples of beliefs, feelings, thoughts, desires and wants and reasons for annotation

Table 3. Beliefs, feelings, thoughts, desires and wants in IPIR Annotation

Examples	Reasons for annotation with [codes]
She wants to have friends	Wanting to have friends is a prerequisite for creating friendships [d750 informal relationship]
He does not want to begin dating	Meanings such as wanting, wishing, interest or desiring etc. or its negation impacts the creation of an intimate relationship [d770 intimate relationships]
Feels distant or cut off from other people	Feelings distant from others impacts forming relationships with others [d779 others unspecified]
Has homicidal thoughts toward his wife Denies homicidal thoughts toward his wife	The type of thoughts toward another provides a quality to a relationship. Code for the particular relationship type described [d770 intimate].
Has homicidal thoughts	Homicidal thoughts are thoughts about harm to another person(s). If no particular relationship can be discerned from the surrounding context, code others unspecified [d779] as the relationship type. Do not annotate the negation of homicidal thoughts, such as “denies homicidal ideation”.

Note: Suicidal thoughts, ideation, plans, intent and suicide attempts are not annotated for IPIR. IPIR is about interactions, relations and relationships with others, not with oneself. See Table 6. Text examples of overlaps/considerations with other ICF domains

IPIR relationships by proxy

As a general principle, any help or assistance given to the patient by a specified other is understood as the person having a relationship with that person. Therefore, information such as “family helps patient with dressing”, or “her neighbors take her to the grocery store” is annotated for the particular relationship type.

IPIR information of interactions by another to the patient (abusive, supportive or otherwise) is annotated as it shows a quality within a relationship the patient is part of. For example, “her husband was supportive”, or “her husband was abusive” are both annotated for IPIR as d770

Intimate relationship. No interaction codes are assigned if there is no interaction information coming from the part of the patient.

6.4 Sentence segmentation

Annotating at the sentence level can pose specific challenges, for example when multiple sentences need to be considered jointly, or when automatic sentence segmentation errors occur. We describe strategies for each challenge below.

Questions and answers are sometimes segmented as different sentences. On their own, they would not be annotated for IPIR, but when considered together for semantics, both would be annotated in the same way as if they were one continuous sentence and meaning. Example of a question-and-answer pair (segmented as 2 sentences):

- Do you feel numb or detached from others, activities, or your surroundings?
- Yes

In such cases, both segments would be coded as d779 (particular interpersonal relationships, other specified and unspecified). Note: The sentence containing the answer needs to be “Yes”, “No” or similar for IPIR annotation. Blank or unknown are not considered IPIR information.

Similarly, when the information needed to determine IPIR presence or IPIR attributes is spread out over two or more sentences because of incorrect sentence segmentation, all necessary sentences would be annotated and coded the same. Below is an example of sentence segmentation that splits relevant information over two sentences:

- He has a good relationship with his
- ex

In this case, both sentences would be coded as *ipir_yes* with the d750 attribute (informal social relationship) set to *true*. The *difficult_to_dermine* value would be *false* for both sentence segments as the IPIR information is clear from the two segments combined.

6.5 Unspecified ICF Codes

In the IPIR schema, General Interpersonal Interactions is given the attribute of “Interaction” that represents the ICF code range from d710 to d729. This range includes d729 General interpersonal interactions, other specified and unspecified. Therefore, annotation of “interaction” includes information that refers to unspecified information that influences the quality of interactions.

In Relationships, however, the d779 unspecified interactions and relationships code is considered a particular relationship type and can be independently selected as an attribute value for annotation. These codes have been defined and operationalized in a previous section, but bear mentioning since in previous annotation domains unspecified ICF codes have not been used. Their incorporation in annotation reflects the inclusion of non-particular relationship types that providers often refer to in their documentation of IPIR information.

6.6 Difficult to determine IPIR sentences

Annotation of IPIR yes/difficult to determine as true can be challenging (see section 4.1). In such cases, code for relationship of d779 for unspecified other unless the sentence is more specific about a particular relationship type, i.e., group, authority, etc. Code for *interaction_true* if evidence of interaction can be ascertained, and code *interaction_false* if evidence of interaction cannot be determined.

6.7 Annotation for IPIR Interaction and/or Relationships

Depending on the IPIR information in a sentence, two combinations of IPIR subclassification coding are possible. These are: (1) BOTH interaction and relationships; or (2) Relationships ONLY/No interaction. Table 4 below provides IPIR text examples with the reasoning and coding for each possible code combinations. Spaces in the text examples denotes where sentences were segmented.

Table 4. IPIR Sentences and Annotation coding: BOTH Interaction AND Relationship

Text Example	Interaction true false	Relationship ICF code	Reasoning
<i>Manner of relating, social skills, and overall presentation was adequate</i>	true	d740 – formal	Strong evidence of interaction skills. Do bring in the context of relation here which is a formal relationship <i>with provider</i> .
<i>She relates adequately with others</i>	true	d779 – others	Strong evidence of interaction skills. Relationship here is with others.
<i>She was dressed casually and adequately groomed Good hygiene Neatly dressed, groomed Dressed in an appropriate, fairly groomed fashion</i>	true	d740 – formal	Dressing and grooming appropriate for the context of an examiner interview is a part of the mRFC criteria, and an important work skill. It can impact interactions. Code interaction and the context of formal relationship with a provider
<i>Eye contact was appropriately focused Poor eye contact</i>	true	d740 – formal	Interaction skills of social cues. Eye contact may be influenced by cultural norms, disposition such as shyness, or symptoms of a condition such as autism.
<i>Vet's behaviors were appropriate during group today</i>	true	d750 - informal	Support groups or peers with a common feature are coded as an informal relationship. Behaviors that were appropriate in group show the quality of the interaction. The type of group had been specified in the context.

<i>Pt participated in session and completed anxiety handout</i>	true	d750 - informal	The context around the sentence showed interaction with a provider. Participation is considered interaction.
<i>Pt shared the reasons why he is here with new patients</i>	true	d750 - informal	The context is within a group. Means the patient is sharing with peers in a group
<i>pt stated that he likes to do things for others and has a hard time asking for help</i>	true	d779 – others	These are feelings, likes, etc. about how the person relates to others. Having a hard time asking for help shows difficulties with interaction skills.
<i>patient reports that prior to that he lived with his father for a brief period but father is reportedly abusive and they do not get along</i>	true	d760 – family	Interaction information is “they do not get along” and referring to a family relationship. We do not capture IPIR information if the patient is the victim. In this case, the patient is the victim. The father is the perpetrator.
<i>He has been increasingly withdrawn, combative, uncooperative, accusatory and believes that people are trying to hurt him and has been screaming and agitated at his mother especially as well as his parents</i>	true	d740 – formal d760 – family d779 - others	Context of the note was during an admission to a health facility. Being combative and uncooperative in context meant with health care providers, formal relationship. One’s beliefs toward others shows a quality to a relationship, in this case “people” are unspecified others. Interactions with mother and parents is qualified.

Table 5. IPIR Sentences and Annotation coding: NO Interaction/ONLY Relationship.

Text Example	Interaction true false	Relationship ICF code	Reasoning
<i>He is especially nervous in crowds</i>	false	d779 – other	No interactions described. Feelings toward others is a quality of relations. A crowd refers to relationship with unspecified others.
<i>Feels distant and cut off from other people</i>	false	d779 – other	No interactions described. Feelings toward others is a quality of relations. “Other people” refers to relationship with unspecified others.
<i>He reports his main stressor has been</i>	false	d750 - informal	No quality of an interaction. Information only about the quality to

<i>dealing with his child's guardian, who is an ex-girlfriend</i>			a relationship. Unless otherwise stated, an ex is considered an informal relationship and no longer an intimate one.
<i>He reports fears that something is happening to her there, since his daughter has run away multiple time</i>	false	d760 – family	No interaction here. Concern for his daughter shows a quality to a relationship
<i>Reports a lot of stress in the family</i>	false	d760 – family	Any conditions that describe a relationship, such as stress or the like, give a quality to the relationship – however no particular interactions are described.
<i>He went to visit his daughter yesterday with his mother and the police</i>	false	d740 – formal d7400 - authority d760 - family	No quality of interaction. Creating some type of temporary relationship with the police (or any other authority figure such as a social worker) is annotated with both d740 formal and particular d7400 as authority figure.
<i>Problem: Family Conflict</i>	false	d760 – family	No interaction described. Only quality to the relationship.
<i>leaning of supportive people in his life</i>	false	d779 – others	It cannot be assumed the supportive people is referring only to family. Supportive people can be formal, like a doctor, informal like a friend, and family. “Supportive persons” are considered general others.
<i>Indicates his ex-wife keeps him from visiting his children</i>	false	d750 – informal d760 - family	Shows a quality to the relationship with ex-wife. Not being able to visit his children impacts maintaining a relationship with children.
<i>He spends his days doing some chores, socializing, walking, and watching television.</i>	false	d779 - others	Socialize always means engaging in behaviors that create or maintain a relationship with other people. No interaction skills described.

6.8 Annotating for multiple domains

It is possible that information on functioning in some IPIR sentences overlaps with information on functioning from other ICF activity chapters such as Self-Care, Domestic Life, Learning and Applying Knowledge, General Tasks and Demands, and Communication. In cases like this, it is important to be aware of and differentiate between the kinds of functioning information being annotated and whether or how to annotate it. Annotations of the IPIR domain should not be influenced by annotations of another domain.

Table 6 provides examples of how functioning information in clinical text can overlap across ICF Activity and Participation domains and the specific focus for annotation.

Table 6. Text examples of overlaps/considerations with other ICF domains

Text examples	IPIR	Learning and Applying Knowledge General Tasks and Demands Communication	Self-care Domestic Life
<p><i>She was dressed casually and adequately groomed</i></p> <p><i>Her hygiene was good</i></p> <p><i>He looked disheveled</i></p>	<p>Only annotate documented observations about the <u>quality of the person's appearance</u> – such as good, poor, adequate, appropriate if it is within the context of an interaction (i.e., with provider, with others, unit staff, etc.)</p>	<p><i>She is independent in grooming and dressing</i> (cognitive capacity information is annotated that includes independence or need for cognitive assist).</p>	<p><i>She is independent in dressing and grooming.</i></p> <p><i>He needs min assist for dressing.</i> (shows ability and level of performance)</p> <p>Dressed appropriately for the season</p>
<p><i>Her eye contact was good</i></p>	<p>Annotated as part of giving social cues. Qualifiers of good, poor etc.</p>	<p>Not annotated. Eye contact is considered a body function, such as WNL or intact.</p>	<p>Not annotated</p>
<p><i>Her husband assists her with dressing</i></p>	<p>Shows a relationship status and quality information</p>	<p>Not annotated</p>	<p>Annotated for self-care assistance with dressing</p>
<p><i>He admitted to having homicidal thoughts toward his ex</i></p>	<p>Homicidal <u>thoughts or attempts</u> are always <u>toward a particular relationship</u> and reflect a quality to that relationship and are annotated.</p>	<p>Only <u>thoughts or thinking</u> is annotated such as homicidal ideation, plans or intent. The relationship is not annotated.</p>	<p>Not annotated</p>

<p><i>She admits to having recent suicidal thoughts</i></p> <p><i>He was admitted for suicidal attempt in the past</i></p>	<p>Not annotated. IPIR is about relations and relationships with others, not with oneself.</p>	<p><u>Thoughts</u> (not attempts) are annotated such as suicidal ideation, plans or intent only if they have or do exist. Negation or not having or denial of suicidal thoughts is <i>not</i> annotated.</p>	<p>Annotated if <u>attempts</u> (not thoughts) of suicide documented as shows not taking care of oneself. Negation of suicidal attempts is also annotated as it shows taking care of oneself.</p>
<p><i>She expressed gratitude to this examiner</i></p>	<p>Communicating appreciation within a formal relationship</p>	<p>Annotated for the communication-producing component</p>	<p>Not annotated</p>
<p><i>His wife helps him to answer the questions</i></p>	<p>Shows a relationship status and quality information</p>	<p>Annotated for the assistance needed for communication</p>	<p>Not annotated</p>

7 IPIR ANNOTATION: FREE-TEXT EXAMPLES

As previously stated in section 1.3 Conceptualizing Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships, four IPIR subcategories were used for conceptualizing IPIR for annotation in the free text of health records. Even though only ICF IPIR codes are used in annotation (see Table 1), IPIR concepts taken from SSA’s mental functioning B criteria and the mental residual functional capacity assessment also informed annotation decisions. This section provides descriptions of IPIR concepts taken from these SSA sources as an additional consideration of information to annotate.

This section presents clinical text examples illustrating inclusion and exclusion criteria for each of the four subcategories used to define IPIR and to help guide IPIR annotation decision-making. The four IPIR subcategories are (1) Interpersonal social skills; (2) Interpersonal social interactions; (3) Interpersonal communication; and (4) Relationships. Interpersonal social skills, social interactions, and communication are annotated using the Interaction code. Relationships are annotated using the Relationship ICF codes.

Annotations of IPIR information is captured without bias as to the type of quality to interactions or relationships (supportive, unsupportive, loving, abusive, etc.).

7.1 Interpersonal Social Skills

Interpersonal social skills are one’s personal skills and abilities needed to be able to interact appropriately. This category includes the ICF IPIR code range of general and specific interactions (d710-d779) and the following IPIR concepts from SSA sources previously mentioned.

Inclusion:

- One’s ability to relate to others.
- Interact appropriately and cooperatively when working with others.
- Handling conflicts in a non-aggressive manner.
- Being respectful and tolerant, and showing appreciation.
- Differentiate responses based on relationships.
- Forming and terminating relationships appropriately.
- Adhering to basic standards of neatness and cleanliness appropriate to the social context, such as being clean and dressing appropriately for work.
- Showing appreciation.

Text examples of interpersonal social skills and reasons for annotating are provided in Table 7 . Table 8 provides text examples that would be excluded for annotation and reasons why.

Table 7. Interpersonal Social Skills: Annotation inclusions

Inclusion Examples of Interpersonal Social skills	Reasons for annotating
<i>He seemed to show very well-developed social skills. Relates well to others.</i>	Straightforward examples of interaction skills without any particular relationship specified. [interaction]
<i>He behaved like a perfect gentleman. He appeared to be a gentleman.</i>	When used as an adjective, the word “gentleman” has implications for social skill behaviors. [interaction]
<i>Has a sense of humor.</i>	Humor is a social skill. The negation of humor, such as when humor is withheld or not expressed when appropriate, is also annotated. [interaction]
<i>She smiled when I entered the room</i>	Demonstration of social cues in relationship with provider. [Interaction]
<i>He identified the following personal strengths: loyalty, sense of humor, neat and organized, and helpful.</i>	Helpful is considered cooperative. [interaction]
<i>He identified the following strengths: “I take people as they come” and “easy to talk to”.</i>	Include self-report information relating to interpersonal social skills. [interaction]
<i>He identified the following personal strengths: “being nice”.</i>	The term “being nice” implies this is behavior toward others. [interaction]
<i>He was agreeable to starting therapy and familiar with his medications.</i>	The word “agreeable” implies cooperation with others. [interaction]
<i>Appeared adequately groomed and casually dressed.</i>	Adequately groomed implies an awareness of being presentable to others socially. [interaction]
<i>Appeared somewhat disheveled.</i>	How one presents to others in appearance is annotated. [interaction]
<i>Patient expressed appreciation of services by this therapist</i>	Shows appreciation in relationships. [Interaction]

Table 8. Interpersonal Social Skills: Exclusion examples and reasons

Exclusion Examples of Interpersonal Social Skills	Reasons for NOT annotating
<i>Instructions - describe the claimant's abilities and limitations in responding appropriately to supervision and to coworkers in a work setting.</i>	This is an instruction statement and has nothing to do with the patient's IPIR.
<i>This gentleman came to my office.</i>	When used as a subject, the word "gentleman" does not have implications for social skills.
<i>Strengths: His compassion for people and animals.</i>	No relation to how disposition of compassion is manifested as IPIR.
<i>He exhibits a positive attitude.</i>	Not specific enough. To include it as a social skill the attitude needs to be towards someone.
<i>Took several breaks and sat with head in hands at table.</i>	Too broad of a statement to be IPIR.
<i>Demonstrates adjustment to illness/Treatment by reflecting understanding; responding appropriately.</i>	Responding appropriately, in this case, is not a social skill. Adjustment to illness means how the person is coping psychologically.
<i>Current Emotional Status-Affect/Mood Patient presents as/with; appropriate.</i>	Appropriate affect or mood refers to body function state only. Mood and affect when described only as a body function without relevance to interactions is not annotated.
<i>Agrees to intervention POC. Agreed to work sautéing vegetables and adding ingredients to the sauce.</i>	"Agrees" simply implies a yes response.

7.2 Interpersonal Social Interactions

Interpersonal social interactions refer to the quality of interactions that occur within a social context. This category includes the ICF IPIR code range of general and specific interactions (d710-d779) and the following IPIR concepts from SSA sources previously mentioned

Inclusion:

- Understanding and/or responding appropriately to physical, emotional, verbal and non-verbal social cues.
- Regulating one's behavior to be socially appropriate such as not being distracting or disruptive to coworkers, or exhibiting excessive irritability, sensitivity, argumentativeness or suspiciousness.

Note: Attendance information, such as to a group, is annotated as it shows efforts toward maintaining a relationship to others that are included in the group. Evidence of participation and cooperation are both indicators of IPIR.

Templated information that includes words associated with IPIR but lack specific information is not annotated, such as "Areas of Occupation affected: Community Participation, Health Management; Social Participation".

Text examples of interpersonal social interactions and reasons for annotating are provided in Table 9. Table 10 provides text examples that would be excluded for annotation and reasons why.

Table 9. Interpersonal Social interactions: Annotation inclusions

Inclusion Examples of Interpersonal Social Interactions	Annotation reasoning and [coding]
<p><i>He was pleasant on approach</i></p> <p><i>He has limited social participation.</i></p> <p><i>With the ability to interact with coworkers and the public, the claimant is markedly impaired.</i></p>	<p>Examples of social interaction information. Context provides information as to the relationship. If one could add “with this therapist/provider” as a suffix, then the relationship is d740 - formal relationship.</p> <p>Limited social participation is a relationship with generalized others d779 [interaction].</p> <p>In the third example, interactions also are within certain relationships [Interaction; d730 strangers; d750 coworkers].</p>
<p><i>Committed a homicidal act.</i></p> <p><i>Homicidal attempt.</i></p>	<p>Annotate information about the person’s behavior or non-behavior as aggressor toward others, predator or perpetrator. (see Exclusion examples for homicidal ideations or plans). [interaction; d779 unspecified others]</p>
<p><i>Her ability to relate is normal.</i></p>	<p>The word "relate" needs to be understood in context and annotated if interaction with others is implied. [Interaction; d779 unspecified others]</p>
<p><i>He sees his grandmother every week and they have tea together.</i></p>	<p>Only capture “seeing” as interaction if it refers to family and friends (see Exclusion examples of “seeing” health providers). [interaction; d760 family relationships]</p>
<p><i>He was able to work with peers with some facilitation.</i></p>	<p>Working with peers implies interaction and maintaining a relationship with peers [interaction; d750 peers]</p>
<p><i>He became more talkative and lively.</i></p> <p><i>She often appeared to feign sleep.</i></p>	<p>Certain behaviors are inferred to occur within a social situation where others are there to perceive them. [Interaction; d740 formal relationship]</p>
<p><i>When he attended groups, (name) engaged well in group discussions though needed cues to recognize the needs of others in sessions.</i></p>	<p>Engaging or participating in group discussion is considered interaction. However, attending a group is not annotated (see exclusion section). [Interaction; d750 peers]</p>
<p><i>His participation was variable.</i></p> <p><i>Regularly participated in OT session. [d740]</i></p> <p><i>Patient participated in a session. [d750]</i></p> <p><i>Participated well in OT group programming. [d750]</i></p> <p><i>Patient worked individually with this writer. [d740]</i></p> <p><i>Joined this writer for therapeutic activities as a means to cope with anxiety and increase feelings of productivity. [d740]</i></p>	<p>It is inferred that the patient is interacting with other people/providers when participating in an individual or group session. If the type of session or group is understood by the context it could be coded as a particular relationship type, such as d740 formal relationship with health care provider, or d750 with peers in a group.</p> <p>All these examples are coded [interaction], with some also having relationship codes (see after examples).</p>

Inclusion Examples of Interpersonal Social Interactions	Annotation reasoning and [coding]
<i>He demonstrated limited tolerance for group setting and structured activities.</i>	Group setting implies a context where interaction with others takes place. [interaction; d750]
<i>During the past 2 weeks, patient has had more difficulty engaging in group activities.</i>	Group activities implies a context where interaction with others takes place. [interaction; d750]
<i>In OT session he volunteered for tasks. [d710-d729] During cooking group he volunteered for tasks. [d710-d729] Patient volunteered to prepare potatoes with a peer. [d710-d729; d750 informal social relationship]</i>	Volunteering implies interaction with another person. The act of volunteering within a group context implies an interaction and cooperation with others. (see Exclusion examples of volunteer work such as “volunteers in the library/fire station”). Examples code [interaction] and also d750 for maintaining singular or group relationships with similar people and peers.
<i>He said he can be a little grumpy with his wife. [interaction; d770] The person became irritable when her husband challenged her delusions [Interaction; d770 intimate relationship] She denied ongoing tantrum behavior. [interaction; d779 other]</i>	Annotate mood and affect if it has strong implications for interactions (such as tantrums, irritability, or aggressiveness). Note: Do not confuse with agitated or other mood states which are only annotated if extends to aggressiveness in social context
<i>It is possible that pt’s reluctance to participate in interview is a result of impaired memory and ability to maintain orientation</i>	The patient’s inability to participate and interact is of interest – despite the reason why. [Interaction; d740 formal relationship]
<i>His mother noted he enjoys Facebook</i>	Social media is included when infers interactions, such as enjoys, uses etc. Relationship with mother implied. [Interaction; d760 family relationship]
<i>It was a pleasure working with her</i>	Proxy IPIR information by the provider. The meaning is “she was pleasant to interact with”. Code as “she was pleasant” [interaction; d740 formal relationship]

Table 10. Interpersonal Social Interactions: Exclusion examples and reasons

Exclusion Examples of Interpersonal Social Interactions	Reasons for NOT annotating
<i>Volunteers in the library.</i>	A general reference to volunteer work has no interaction information.
<i>Homicidal ideation, plan or intent.</i>	Ideation or plan is not a behavior. Ideation is body function (b160 Thought functions).
<i>He left her even though he was the one doing the cheating.</i>	Do not annotate marital status such as divorce, married, cheating etc.
<i>He often required encouragement to attend. He needed repetition to follow discussions. He preferred to focus on his own interests and needs unless prompted.</i>	Do not annotate interaction that refers to the type of assist being given, such as prompting or supervision. Requiring encouragement or needing repetition is considered an assist.
<i>Was redirectable.</i>	This statement is too broad and also implies some sort of assist.

Exclusion Examples of Interpersonal Social Interactions	Reasons for NOT annotating
<i>Throughout his admission he was an active participant.</i>	“Throughout admission” is too broad a term. Active participation does not necessarily imply interpersonal interaction. Needs more specificity.
<i>He generally followed along with discussions and activities.</i>	Followed along implies more cognitive skills and doesn't specify that the person participated in the discussions.
<i>This writer will continue to work with patient and his family via phone and email to support his efforts in obtaining financial resources.</i>	Do not annotate what the provider plans to do, even if it relates to IPIR.
<i>Regularly attended OT session. Participated in OT activities. OT programming He showed willingness to participate in a variety of activities.</i>	Attendance does not imply interaction. “Activities” or “programming” are terms that are too broad to infer interactions. Participating in activities is broad and doesn't necessarily imply interactions.
<i>Was willing to participate in activities when given concrete tasks and examples</i>	This is about more cognitive assist by adapting the task so person will participate. See example above.
<i>During session, patient joined in activity related to mental health recovery.</i>	Activities or therapeutic activities are too broad of terms and do not necessarily imply any social interactions.
<i>He is guarded talking about psychotic symptoms.</i>	Terms such as guarded refer to a person's disposition – disposition is a body function.
<i>Goals: Participate in OT cooking group</i>	Do not annotate this group as the goals is for ADL and not IPIR. Goals are only annotated if they relate to IPIR and have been met or partially met.
<i>Presented with anxious, agitated mood and flat affect. Current Emotional Status-Affect/Mood Agitated; Anxious; Flat.</i>	Moods are a state of body functions. They can occur in the absence of any social context. “Agitated” or “irritable” are emotional states that are documented simply as an observation without IPIR implications.
<i>History of emotional and behavior problems Pt. denies.</i>	Do not annotate Behavioral problems as term is too broad, though behavioral problems do often have implications for social interactions.
<i>States that he sees psychiatrist and therapist weekly.</i>	“Seeing” a mental health provider does not imply interactions. In clinical context/situation there needs to be more content on the quality of interaction.
<i>Pt briefly discussed her moods, stating that she gets angry and “I throw things”.</i>	Throwing things can be done without interacting with someone. This example is too ambiguous.
<i>She appeared to be somewhat sedated by medication during this examination.</i>	This is a state of body function, not IPIR.
<i>He has a lot of anger issues</i>	No social context.

7.3 Interpersonal Communications

Interpersonal communication refers to verbal and non-verbal communication that occurs within a social context. This category includes the ICF IPIR code range of general and specific

interactions (d710-d779) and the following IPIR concepts from SSA sources previously mentioned.

Inclusion:

- Initiating or sustaining a conversation.
- Stating one’s own point of view in a socially appropriate manner.
- Making one’s needs known to others
- Requesting help or assistance when needed.
- Asking simple questions, answering questions, and providing explanations.
- Accepting instructions and responding appropriately to requests, suggestions, correction, challenges and criticism from others, such as supervisors or peers.

Text examples of interpersonal communication and reasons for annotating are provided in Table 11 . Table 12 provides text examples that would be excluded for annotation and reasons why.

Table 11. Interpersonal Communication: Annotation inclusions

Inclusion Examples of Interpersonal Communication	Reasons for annotating and [codes]
<i>Has the ability to accept instructions from supervisors.</i>	Implies a quality of communication with another person in a position of authority [Interaction; d740 formal relationship; d7400 relating with persons in authority]
<i>Needed redirection to answer the question.</i>	Provides a quality that answering questions is difficult. [Interaction; d740]
<i>Readily answered questions related to daily occupations.</i>	Answering questions is a clear example of communication within context of with another person. However, the quality of the communication – of readily answered – is IPIR [Interaction; d740]
<i>History of suicide attempt and/or aggressive behavior. Pt unable/ refuses to answer. Patient indicated her understanding but still refused to answer any questions re: ETOH use and mental health care. Pt unable/refuses to answer.</i>	Refusing to answer a question, though a person’s right, is considered as a barrier to a provider obtaining information requested through verbal communication. Deliberately not answering a question is the negation of answering a question – something included in the definition of IPIR. [Interaction; d740]
<i>Was dependent on his mother to respond to most of the questions</i>	Shows quality of answering questions. [Interaction; d760 family relationships]
<i>She had difficulty generating spontaneous follow-up questions and statements in conversations but was willing to practice these skills in structured settings.</i>	Mentioning quality of interactions in conversations is annotated. [Interaction; d740]
<i>Communication/Interaction skills: Is articulate and able to make his needs known.</i>	“Articulate” in this case means able to express oneself clearly to others. To make one’s needs known is a communication skill. [Interaction; d740]
<i>Communication style: Pt is soft spoken but can be drawn into conversation.</i>	Only include soft spoken if it tells something about how it affects the interaction. [Interaction; d740]

Table 12. Interpersonal communication: Exclusion examples and reasons

Exclusion Examples of Interpersonal Communication	Reasons for NOT annotating
Needs supervision. Needs prompting. Was redirected.	Needs specificity and/or quality of the interactions.
His speech showed very good articulation and fluency.	“Articulate” in this case refers to a body function.
She discussed with writer strategies to minimize discussions.	Don't capture discuss or pt. reports as only a fact without any quality of the interaction itself
Pt verbalizes understanding.	Understanding something is a cognitive function. Verbalizing is a body function meaning to speak.
Pt is soft spoken.	“Soft-spoken” can have many meanings. Do not include soft spoken unless it tells you something about how it affects the interaction.
She responded to questions in a very concrete manner.	Information is more about cognition and refers to the way the patient is thinking (in a concrete manner). This is not about a quality of interaction with the provider.

7.4 Relationships

Any interaction implies some sort of “relationship” with a person. Interactions occur within social relationships with people (strangers, friends, relatives, family members, etc.). What is of interest is the quality of that relationship. This category includes the ICF IPIR code range of Particular Interpersonal Relationships (d730-d799) and the following IPIR concepts from SSA sources previously mentioned.

Inclusion:

The types of social relationships can be:

- Formal or informal.
- Range from private to public and include supervisors and co-workers.
- Relationships that provide ongoing psychosocial support(s) that help to mitigate the symptoms and signs of any mental health difficulties.

Text examples of relationships and reasons for annotating are provided in Table 13. Table 14 provides text examples that would be excluded for annotation and reasons why.

Table 13. Relationships: Annotation inclusions

Inclusion Examples of Relationships and [codes]	Reasons for annotating
She feels close to her daughters. [d760] She had a good relationship with her grandmother. [d760] Reports strained family relationships. [d760] He helps his grandmother. [d760]	Descriptions about the quality of relationships with family members are considered to be IPIR. Quality descriptions may be positive or negative, and sometimes inferred from the behavior (such as helpful to grandmother, grumpy with wife, etc.)

Inclusion Examples of Relationships and [codes]	Reasons for annotating
<i>Patient reports that he has friends. [d750]</i> <i>He has an old friend who lives nearby. [d750]</i>	There is some effort involved in making and keeping a relationship with friends.
<i>He wants to have friends. [d750]</i> <i>She wants to date. [d770]</i>	A desire or want to have friends or a close relationship is a first step toward forming a relationship. Dating implies a more intimate relationship.
<i>Reported that she is not interested in making friends. [d750]</i>	Capture the negation of IPIR wants or desires.
<i>They have been friends for 20 years. [d750]</i> <i>She married in 2007 and is still married [d770]</i>	The length of time implies a quality of friendship that has endured for many years.
<i>He stated that he was looking forward to celebrating his son's second birthday. [d760]</i>	Shows the quality and maintenance of a relationship with son [d760 Family relationships].
<i>Patient has a strong support system derived from his two daughters, siblings, parents, co-workers, and spouse. [d750; d760; d770]</i>	Support is annotated if is referring to psychosocial support. Receiving psychosocial support from others implies a relationship.
<i>He will continue receiving support from his brother. [d760]</i> <i>She would benefit from her family's continued support in using these cognitive strategies. [d760]</i>	The word "continued" is key as means the person was already receiving some type of support from family members.
<i>Would benefit from continued support and supervision from his brother and other family members. [d760]</i>	"Benefit" implies a recommendation and if relates to IPIR is annotated if it is something that is currently happening.
<i>Identified Support Networks: Extended family/friends. [d750; d760]</i> <i>Pt notes that her friends and children help her cope. [d750; d760]</i> <i>Patient has a strong support system derived from his two daughters, siblings, parents, co-workers, and spouse. [d750; d760; d770]</i>	Support network or system implies psychosocial support from those persons mentioned and a quality to a relationship.
<i>Source of income: spouse/partner wages [d770]</i> <i>Patient is also financially supported by a benefactor. [d779]</i> <i>Reported that she received financial help from a friend. [d750]</i> <i>Currently relies on daily spending money from his parents. [d760]</i>	Financial support either received or given is annotation as IPIR relationship with no interaction.
<i>Family drives him to appointments. [d760]</i> <i>Mother helps manage his medications. [d760]</i> <i>His family visits every day. [d760]</i> <i>Her friends bring her meals. [d750]</i> <i>His girlfriend was by his bedside. [d770]</i>	Proxy IPIR information of others doing things for the patient or simply being present with the patient implies a relationship.

Inclusion Examples of Relationships and [codes]	Reasons for annotating
<p><i>He has a caregiver that comes 3 x/weekly. [d740]</i> <i>He sees his psychiatrist weekly. [d740]</i> <i>Her housekeeper comes every two weeks [d740]</i></p>	<p>A regular frequency of contact with another implies some sort of relationship. In these cases it is a formal relationship.</p>
<p><i>He relies on his family support for IADL activities. [d760]</i> <i>Her mother helps her with bathing and dressing. [d760]</i></p>	<p>Information about another helping the person with their ADLs or IADLs is annotated as it shows a relationship with that person.</p>
<p><i>Enjoys spending time with family. [d760]</i> <i>She is afraid of strangers. [d730]</i></p>	<p>Descriptions of emotions expressed by being with specific persons implies a quality in a relationship – both positive and negative.</p>
<p><i>Priorities: "My girlfriend". [d770]</i> <i>Caregiver: Wife [d770]</i></p>	<p>Implies the presence of a type of relationship.</p>
<p><i>Stated that he generally eats meals with his family. [d760]</i> <i>Shares meals prepared by his mother. [d760]</i> <i>He goes out to eat with his wife. [d770]</i></p>	<p>Eating meals with others shows a relationship but not necessarily any interaction.</p>
<p><i>Social Participation: Reported attending local clubhouse. [d779]</i></p>	<p>Attending a group, or a place where groups meet, is maintaining a relationship with others</p>
<p><i>Pt's wife works out of the home during the day, but she calls pt. 10+ times/day to check on him at home. [d760]</i></p>	<p>Calling 10+ times/day to check on someone implies a quality to a familial relationship.</p>
<p><i>Pt feels comfortable at church and his church community understands his problems. [d779]</i></p>	<p>A church community or other such groups is understood as a group of people. Relationship with community of people is implied.</p>
<p><i>Patient reported mixed feelings about her recent break-up with her boyfriend. [d770]</i> <i>In session on [Date], patient shared some about break-up with her boyfriend. [d770]</i></p>	<p>The ending of a romantic or intimate relationships is IPIR due to the negation of creating and maintaining a relationship.</p>
<p><i>Caring for his elderly grandparents. [d760]</i> <i>His sister is his caregiver [d760]</i></p>	<p>Implies relationship whether by the patient directly to another, or proxy by another's relationship to the patient.</p>
<p><i>Patient resides with friend. [d750]</i> <i>Lives with his parents. [d760]</i> <i>He currently lives with his wife. [d770]</i></p>	<p>Cohabitation implies a relationship is likely to exist with the other person/persons</p>
<p><i>He is relieved that his tax accountant is helping since he is self-employed. [d740]</i></p>	<p>Shows a relationship with a person hired for services.</p>

Exclusion: A sentence that only infers a familial relationship without any description in the text or surrounding context that the relationship is created or maintained is not annotated.

Relationships must show some type of quality to the relationship to be included in annotation as a Relationship. Exception is friends or if quality of the familial relationship is specified.

Table 14. Relationships: Exclusion examples and reasons

Exclusion Examples of Relationship	Reasons for NOT annotating
<i>Patient reports she has an older sister</i>	Simply stating that one has a child, brother etc., is not annotated unless there is evidence in context of creating or maintaining the relationship
<i>She has a 10-year-old daughter</i>	Does not imply an interaction or relationship. Too broad.
<i>She is presently under the care of mental health professionals.</i>	"Public" is broad term. Relationship but no quality. We would need to have the "why" show quality.
<i>"I don't like the public".</i>	Too broad. Could mean playing alone etc.
<i>He expressed that he had a good childhood.</i>	Too broad.
<i>Functioning generally in society.</i>	Exhibiting an attitude without IPIR-related context is too broad.
<i>He exhibits a positive attitude.</i>	Plan development does not imply others contributing besides the patient.
<i>Family/Patient Involved in Plan Development Yes.</i>	Recommendations are not annotated. Services and OT sessions are too broad by themselves unless IPIR is related to this information.
<i>Recommend continued engagement with mental health services.</i> <i>Recommend continue OT sessions.</i>	"Identifying the topic of interest" i.e., social support is not a behavior.
<i>In Goals - identify 3 topics of interest such as building social support.</i>	Hypothetical statement in the future of a relationship that does not currently exist.
<i>Patient believes in God and did indicate that daily interaction with a chaplain while here would be supportive.</i>	No presence of IPIR information
<i>She reported surviving financially without the assistance of her parents</i>	Do not annotate what the therapist did.
<i>Have been meeting w/ the pt. weekly to provide supportive counseling.</i>	He is helping at a place – not enough information to show a relationship with a mother.
<i>He attempts to help at his mother's house barn about once a week.</i>	Being accompanied by staff is only information about transport method.
<i>Staff accompanied the patient to the gym.</i>	Relationship information of someone who has died does not fall in the "creating and maintaining" definition.
<i>He is coping with the death of his cousin who is also his best friend.</i>	

8 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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Appendix 1: ICF Interpersonal Interactions & Relationships Codes and Definitions

These ICF Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR) codes are the codes published and available on the ICF browser at the time the guideline was developed. The ICF continues to add codes to the online browser. We recommended users check the [ICF online browser](#) for the most updated classification and codes.

The table below displays ICF IPIR codes and definitions with 3-digit parent codes and their 4-digit child codes. Annotation was done using all seven 3-digit IPIR codes and one additional 4-digit code for specificity. All codes used for annotation in the table below are bolded and highlighted. Other 4-digit child codes are displayed with definitions provided for the benefit of the reader to provide greater conceptual clarity to the parent code.

CHAPTER 7 ICF (from ICF Browser)	
INTERPERSONAL INTERACTIONS AND RELATIONSHIPS	
This chapter is about carrying out the actions and tasks required for basic and complex interactions with people (strangers, friends, relatives, family members and lovers) in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.	
General interpersonal interactions (d710-d729)	
d710 Basic interpersonal interactions	
Interacting with people in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by showing consideration and esteem when appropriate, or responding to the feelings of others. <i>Inclusions: showing respect, warmth, appreciation, and tolerance in relationships; responding to criticism and social cues in relationships; and using appropriate physical contact in relationships</i>	
d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships	Showing and responding to consideration and esteem, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.
d7101 Appreciation in relationships	Showing and responding to satisfaction and gratitude, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.
d7102 Tolerance in relationships	Showing and responding to understanding and acceptance of behavior, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.
d7103 Criticism in relationships	Providing and responding to implicit and explicit differences of opinion or disagreement, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.
d7104 Social cues in relationships	Giving and reacting appropriately to signs and hints that occur in social interactions.
d7105 Physical contact in relationships	Making and responding to bodily contact with others, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.
d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons	Showing differential responses to individuals, such as by reaching out for the familiar person and differentiating them from strangers and reacting in an appropriate manner.
d720 Complex interpersonal interactions	
Maintaining and managing interactions with other people, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by regulating emotions and impulses, controlling verbal and physical aggression, acting	

independently in social interactions, and acting in accordance with social rules and conventions, when for example playing, studying or working with others. <i>Inclusions: forming and terminating relationship; regulating behaviors within interactions; interacting according to social rules; and maintaining social space.</i>	
d7200 Forming relationships	Beginning and maintaining interactions with others for a short or long period of time, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by introducing oneself, finding and establishing friendships and professional relationships, starting a relationship that may become permanent, romantic or intimate.
d7201 Terminating relationships	Bringing interactions to a close in a contextually and socially appropriate manner, such as by ending temporary relationships at the end of a visit, ending long-term relationships with friends when moving to a new town or ending relationships with work colleagues, professional colleagues and service providers, and ending romantic or intimate relationships.
d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions	Regulating emotions and impulses, verbal aggression and physical aggression in interactions with others, in a contextually and socially appropriate manner.
d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Acting independently in social interactions and complying with social conventions governing one's role, position or other social status in interactions with others.
d7204 Maintaining social space	Being aware of and maintaining a distance between oneself and others that is contextually, socially and culturally appropriate.
Particular interpersonal relationships (d730-d779)	
d730 Relating with strangers Engaging in temporary contacts and links with strangers for specific purposes, when asking for directions or other information, or making a purchase.	
d740 Formal relationships Creating and maintaining specific relationships in formal settings, such as with teachers, employers, professionals or service providers. <i>Inclusions: relating with persons in authority, with subordinates and with equals</i>	
d7400 Relating with persons in authority	Creating and maintaining formal relations with people in positions of power of a higher rank or prestige relative to one's own position, such as an employer.
d7401 Relating with subordinates	Creating and maintaining formal relations with people in positions of lower rank or prestige relative to one's own social position, such as an employee or servant.
d7402 Relating with equals	Creating and maintaining formal relations with people in the same position of authority, rank or prestige relative to one's own social position.
d750 Informal social relationships Entering into relationships with others, such as casual relationships with people living in the same community or residence, or with co-workers, students, playmates, people with similar backgrounds or professions. <i>Inclusions: informal relationships with friends, neighbors, acquaintances, co-inhabitants and peers</i>	

d7500 Informal relationships with friends	Creating and maintaining friendship relationships that are characterized by mutual esteem and common interests.
d7501 Informal relationships with neighbors	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people who live in nearby dwellings or living areas.
d7502 Informal relationships with acquaintances	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people whom one knows but who are not close friends.
d7503 Informal relationships with co-inhabitants	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people who are co-inhabitants of a house or other dwelling, privately or publicly run, for any purpose.
d7504 Informal relationships with peers	Creating and maintaining informal relationships with people who share the same age, interest or other common feature.
d760 Family relationships	
Creating and maintaining kinship relationships, such as those with members of the nuclear family, extended family, foster and adopted family and step-relationships, more distant relationships such as second cousins, or legal guardians.	
<i>Inclusions: parent-child and child-parent relationships, sibling and extended family relationships</i>	
d7600 Parent-child relationships	Becoming and being a parent, both natural and adoptive, such as by having a child and relating to it as a parent or creating and maintaining a parental relationships with an adoptive child, and providing physical, intellectual and emotional nurture to one's natural or adoptive child.
d7601 Child-parent relationships	Creating and maintaining relationships with one's parent, such as a young child obeying his or her parents or an adult child taking care of his or her elderly parents.
d7602 Sibling relationships	Creating and maintaining a brotherly or sisterly relationship with a person who shares one or both parents by birth, adoption or marriage.
d7603 Extended family relationships	Creating and maintaining a family relationship with members of one's extended family, such as with cousins, aunts and uncles and grandparents.
d770 Intimate relationships	
Creating and maintaining close or romantic relationships between individuals, such as husband and wife, lovers or sexual partners. <i>Inclusions: romantic, spousal and sexual relationships</i>	
d7700 Romantic relationships	Creating and maintaining a relationship based on emotional and physical attraction, potentially leading to long-term intimate relationships.
d7701 Spousal relationships	Creating and maintaining an intimate relationship of a legal nature with another person, such as in a legal marriage, including becoming and being a legally married wife or husband or an unmarried spouse.
d7702 Sexual relationships	Creating and maintaining a relationship of a sexual nature, with a spouse or other partner.

Appendix 2: Crosswalk of SSA criteria of mental functioning to related ICF b and d codes and IPIR annotation codes

Interactions with others is one of four criteria that the United States Social Security Administration (SSA) uses to document a claimant's mental functioning capacity for work disability determination. To support SSA as our use case, we have applied NLP methods to extract interpersonal interactions and relationships (IPIR) information using the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF) as our framework. The purpose of this crosswalk is to ensure ICF IPIR coding used in annotations comprehensively represented SSA policy language related to interactions with others.

SSA's policy language in this document to determine a mental functioning disability arises from two SSA sources: (1) The B2 criteria of the listings of mental disorders for adults (Social Security Administration, 2024), and (2) the Mental Residual Functional Capacity Assessment (MRFC) section C of interact with others. The listings of mental disorders for adults are the criteria by which SSA determines mental functioning disability. The MRFC assessment is an additional document adjudicators use to record a summary of their conclusions, derived from evidence in a claimant's file, that ranks the level of mental activity limitations within the context of the claimant's capacity to sustain a normal workday and workweek on an ongoing basis.

To provide context, all areas and criteria of mental functioning disability determination by SSA are outlined below. The bolded and highlighted areas are the specific criteria relating to IPIR information that will be addressed in the crosswalk and are the focus of this document.

The four areas of the **Mental Residual Functional Capacity Assessment** are:

- A. Understanding and Memory
- B. Sustained concentration and Persistence
- C. Social Interaction**
- D. Adaptation

The four areas, referred to as the **B Criteria, in SSA Adult Mental Disorders** are:

- B1. Understand, remember, or apply information
- B2. **Interact with others**
- B3. Concentrate, persist, or maintain pace
- B4. Adapt or manage oneself

SSA's B2 criteria primarily refer to one's abilities to relate to and work with supervisors, co-workers, and the public. Though the language from the listings of SSA's B2 criteria for adult mental disorders and SSA's MRFC Assessment Section C are similar, there are some differences. Therefore, in Table 1 below, language from the listings of [SSA's B2 criteria](#) for adult mental

disorders are shown in blue font and SSA's **MRFC Assessment Section C** are shown in green font.

We recognize that clinical documentation of mental functioning information is often written at the level of body functions, therefore both body function (ICF b-codes) and activity functioning (ICF d-codes) are included in this crosswalk to help annotators decide how mentions of mental functions and mental functioning might be represented in IPIR activities and participation codes. Bolded codes are parent ICF 3-digit codes. The listed 4-digit ICF codes are shown to give more specificity and conceptual clarity to SSA mental functioning concepts. ICF codes from other activity domains that could apply, such as Communication and Applying Knowledge, are included in the crosswalk and italicized but were not used in the IPIR annotation schema; these are shown with their chapter headings and code ranges. The last column in Appendix Table 1 lists the ICF codes actually used for annotation of IPIR functioning information in health records related to our work; they are shown in bold font.

Appendix Table 1. Crosswalk of SSA Criteria for interaction with others to ICF body and activity functioning codes and codes used for IPIR annotation.

12.00 Mental Disorders - Adult	ICF Codes		
SSA B2- Criteria Mental RFC - C	ICF b-codes Body Function – Mental Functions	ICF d-codes Activities/Participation	ICF codes used for IPIR annotation
<p>abilities to <i>relate to and work with supervisors, coworkers, and the public</i></p> <p>The ability to <i>get along with coworkers or peers without distracting them or exhibiting behavioral extremes</i></p> <p>The ability to <i>interact appropriately with the general public</i></p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions</p> <p>b126 Temperament and personality functions</p> <p>b1261 Agreeableness</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions</p> <p>d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships</p> <p>d7101 Appreciation in relationships</p> <p>d7102 Tolerance in relationships</p> <p>d7103 Criticism in relationships</p> <p>d7104 Social cues in relationships</p> <p>d7105 Physical contact in relationships</p> <p>d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons</p> <p>d720 Complex interpersonal interactions</p> <p>d7200 Forming relationships</p> <p>d7201 Terminating relationships</p> <p>d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions</p> <p>d7203 Interacting according to social rules</p> <p>d730 Relating with strangers</p> <p>d740 Formal relationships</p> <p>d7400 Relating with persons in authority</p> <p>d7401 Relating with subordinates</p> <p>d7402 Relating with equals</p> <p>d750 Informal social relationships</p> <p>d7504 Informal relationships with peers</p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729)</p> <p>d730 Relating with strangers</p> <p>d740 Formal relationships</p> <p>d7400 Relating with persons in authority</p> <p>d750 Informal social relationships</p>
<p><i>cooperating with others</i></p>	<p>b122 Global psychosocial functions</p> <p>b126 Temperament and personality functions</p> <p>b1261 Agreeableness</p>	<p>d710 Basic interpersonal interactions</p> <p>d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships</p> <p>d7102 Tolerance in relationships</p> <p>d7103 Criticism in relationships</p> <p>d720 Complex interpersonal interactions</p> <p>d7200 Forming relationships</p> <p>d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions</p> <p>d7203 Interacting according to social rules</p> <p>d730 Relating with strangers</p> <p>d740 Formal relationships</p>	<p>Interactions (d710-d729)</p> <p>d730 Relating with strangers</p> <p>d740 Formal relationships</p> <p>d750 Informal social relationships</p>

		d750 Informal social relationships	
<i>asking for help when needed</i> <i>The ability to ask simple questions or request assistance</i>	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight b167 Mental functions of language	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7100 Respect and warmth in relationships d7101 Appreciation in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships <i>d138</i> Acquiring information <i>d330</i> Speaking <i>d3301</i> Producing simple spoken messages <i>d3302</i> Producing complex spoken messages	Interactions (d710-d729) d730 Relating with strangers d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships
<i>handling conflicts with others</i>	b122 Global psychosocial functions b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships <i>d175</i> Solving problems <i>d240</i> Handling stress and other psychological demands	Interactions (d710-d729) d740 Formal relationships d750 Informal social relationships
<i>stating own point of view</i>	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1266 Confidence b167 Mental functions of language	<i>d330</i> Speaking <i>d3302</i> Producing complex spoken messages	No IPIR code
<i>initiating or sustaining conversation</i>	b122 Global psychosocial functions b167 Mental functions of language	<i>(d330-d349)</i> Communicating - producing <i>d350</i> Conversation <i>d3501</i> Sustaining a conversation	No IPIR code
<i>understanding and responding to social cues (physical, verbal, emotional)</i>	b122 Global psychosocial functions b167 Mental functions of language	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Interactions (d710-d729)

		d7204 Maintaining social space <i>d315 Communicating with - receiving - nonverbal messages</i> <i>d335 Producing nonverbal messages</i> <i>d3350 Producing body language</i>	
responding to requests, suggestions, criticism, correction, and challenges The ability to accept instructions and respond appropriately to criticism from supervisors.	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1643 Cognitive flexibility b1644 Insight	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7103 Criticism in relationships d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules d740 Formal relationships	Interactions (d710-d729) d740 Formal relationships
keeping social interactions free of excessive irritability, sensitivity, argumentativeness or suspiciousness	b126 Temperament and personality functions b1261 Agreeableness b1263 Psychic stability b152 Emotional functions b1520 Appropriateness of emotion b1521 Regulation of emotion	d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Interactions (d710-d729)
The ability to maintain socially appropriate behavior	b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1644 Insight	d710 Basic interpersonal interactions d7101 Appreciation in relationships d7102 Tolerance in relationships d7103 Criticism in relationships D7104 Social cues in relationships d7105 Physical contact in relationships d7106 Differentiation of familiar persons d720 Complex interpersonal interactions d7200 Forming relationships d7201 Terminating relationships d7202 Regulating behaviors within interactions d7203 Interacting according to social rules	Interactions (d710-d729)
...adhere to basic standards of neatness and cleanliness	b114 Orientation Functions b164 Higher-level cognitive functions b1645 Judgement	d720 Complex interpersonal interactions <i>d177 Making decisions</i>	Interactions (d710-d729)

Appendix 3: Annotated Note for IPIR

Below is a synthetic occupational therapy evaluation note that has been annotated for Interpersonal Interactions and Relationships (IPIR) information according to the provided legend. Note that any information that resembles PII or PHI does not pertain to any real individual. Also note that for clarity, it is assumed that this document does not have sentence segmentation issues so that the focus is on IPIR annotation. Annotating IPIR in incorrectly segmented sentences poses its own challenges, for which we describe strategies in Section 6.4.

Legend:

- *ipir_yes* sentence
- *ipir_no* sentence

OCCUPATIONAL THERAPY EVALUATION NOTE

Details:

Visit Type During This Encounter: Inpatient

Date Of Evaluation Visit: 05/01/2020

Diagnosis: Schizophrenia

Additional Referrals To RMD Services: Recreation therapy; Vocational rehab

English As Preferred Language For Healthcare: Yes

Subjective:

Patient/Others Comments: Corey Finch is a 23-year old male currently living with his parents. He was pleasant though reserved on approach and agreeable to participate in interview. Affect was blunted but able to smile at times, though eye contact was poor. He answered questions with short replies and latency noted in response to questions. He reported that his main concerns at this time are his "disturbing thoughts."

Objective:

Observations/Interview Data: Corey was seen for occupational therapy evaluation on 5/9/20, OT Cooking Group on 5/6/20, and an AMPS (Assessment of Motor and Process Skills) on 5/12/20. Occupational performance was analyzed via chart review, interview, standardized assessment of ADL/IADL performance, and direct observation of performance in a group setting.

Evaluation yielded the following:

Occupational Profile Performance in Areas of Occupation Activities of Daily Living (ADL): Casually dressed; adequately groomed. Reported that he takes care of daily grooming without reminders.

Instrumental Activities of Daily Living (IADL):

Community Mobility: Reported that he has a driver's license. Gave conflicting information about whether he has been driving recently. It appears that he currently relies on his family to transport him as needed.

Financial Management: Reported receiving SSDI which is deposited in his account. Reported that he budgets his money appropriately and manages his own account. Stated that his parents supplement his financial support as needed.

Health Management: Reported that his parents assist with setting up and getting him to medical appointments. Stated that his mother helps set up his medications in a pill box but that he takes them on his own and may forget a dose approximately once or twice a week. Able to name the names and doses of his antipsychotic medication.

Home Management & Meal Prep: Corey was vague about his responsibilities/participation in household tasks. Reported that he is responsible for some household tasks such as washing dishes, taking out the trash, and caring for family pets. Stated that he does not do his own laundry. He reported that he helps his mother with cooking sometimes and if he wants to make himself food, he will prepare something simple like oatmeal or a sandwich.

Shopping: Corey is not responsible for shopping for household supplies. He reported shopping independently for personal items.

Education: Corey graduated from HS. He attended a 4-year college full-time for two years and part-time for another year, studying marine biology. He was unable to continue after the onset of symptoms. Reported that he would like to complete his degree.

Work: Corey reported that his last job was "a while back" during summers when he worked as a lifeguard at a local community swimming pool.

Leisure: listening to music, following sports, following current events/watching news programs

Social Participation: It does not appear that Corey has social contact with anyone outside of his immediate family. Reported withdrawing from friends after the onset of his symptoms and does not identify any current friends or social activities. Stated that he gets very anxious in social situations, especially around women who might think "I'm weird."

Client Factors: Corey lost his 10-year-old sister and only sibling when he was 8 years old due to a motor vehicle accident. He reported that he was on the swim team in high school and college before he had to drop out. He has been discouraged by his recent weight gain and he is interested in getting back to swimming. Corey was reluctant to discuss the specific nature of his symptoms but reported that his "intrusive thoughts make it hard to function" and he feels "depressed" about his situation. He reported drowsiness from his medications which causes him difficulty "just getting up and going."

Pain: No pain, 0/10, elicited, observed or reported during this visit

Occupational Performance Skills/Patterns: Corey participated in the Assessment of Motor and Processing Skills (AMPS) on 5/12/20. The AMPS is a standardized evaluation of a person's ability to perform personal and domestic activities of daily living (ADL) tasks. More specifically, when a person is evaluated using the AMPS, the occupational therapist observes the person perform at least two relevant and chosen ADL tasks. The assessment results are as follows: Performance Skills Motor Skills: (Skills needed to move self and objects)

Effort: Demonstrated average clumsiness and effort during IADL task performance

Areas of difficulty: manipulating objects.

The ADL motor ability measure was 0.8 standard deviations above the normative mean, indicating that 21.1% of healthy, well people the same age likely have a higher ADL motor ability measure.

Process Skills: (Skills needed to organize and adapt actions to complete task)

Efficiency: Demonstrated mild degree of disorganization and undesirable use of time, space, or objects. The ADL process ability measure was 1.3 standard deviations below the normative mean, indicating that 90.5% of healthy, well people the same age likely have a higher ADL process ability measure.

Safety: Demonstrated minimal risk for personal injury or environmental damage.

Need for assistance: Demonstrated a minimal degree of need for verbal assistance.

Areas of difficulty: applying knowledge, temporal organization, organizing space and objects, and adapting performance.

Community needs: daily supervision is recommended in the community.

Communication/Interaction Skills: Corey is pleasant and able to make his needs known.

However, during the interview and in group setting, Corey appeared preoccupied and had some difficulty attending to interactions. Responded when directly addressed but no spontaneous interactions and there was latency in his responses. Asked for questions to be repeated frequently. However, is well-spoken and able to answer questions appropriately though responses were brief and vague. Able to smile in response to humor.

Habits/Routines/Roles: Corey reported that at home he generally gets up in the late morning (11 AM-12PM) and spends a great deal of time on his computer or engaged in other solitary or passive activities. He used to swim at his local pool 3-4 times a week but stated, "I haven't done that in a while." He appears to have an established ADL/grooming routine though sometimes needs reminders. Reported that he feels he has let his parents down but acknowledges his parents are supportive.

Affected Areas of Occupation: Activities of daily living; Instrumental activities of daily living; Leisure; Education; Vocation; Social participation

Assessment:

Corey's occupational profile is characterized by modified independence in ADL performance with some difficulty managing IADL, Leisure, Vocation/Education, and Social roles due to experience of symptoms. Though he has been able to live independently in a college setting in the past, he currently relies on the support of his parents. His health condition has limited his present repertoire of occupations and interfered with his ability to achieve age-appropriate roles such as finishing college, working and establishing independent living. His social and community participation are currently very limited. Corey is in the beginning stages of understanding his health condition. He appears motivated to learn more about his health condition and explore options for managing his symptoms. Corey would benefit from occupational therapy services while on the unit to improve engagement in occupations to support participation in desired roles and life situations in home and community.

Strengths: Corey's strengths include willingness to participate in therapy, his past educational and social experiences, his past experience in a variety of leisure activities, and generally cooperative attitude. He identified the following personal strengths: "swimming" and "sciences."

Needs: Corey's needs include further development of coping skills to support engagement in college and work and increasing social/community participation, establishing a health daily routine, and increasing independence in IADLs. Corey identified the following needs: "social skills" and "improve fitness."

Priorities: "get better, lose weight, and finish degree"

NIHFA OT Score (6-24): 23

Need For Other RMD Services: The Patient has been referred to Vocational therapy and Recreational therapy services.

Plan:

Evaluation & Interventions To Be Coordinated With Interdisciplinary Team:

Interventions: Occupational Therapy to be initiated at this time with individual services as specific needs are identified and unit-based programming per tolerance/availability throughout admission. His progress will be reported in treatment planning meeting on a weekly basis.

Goals:

STGs (within 2 weeks): Corey will:

1. attend next OT Cooking Group session and participate in at least 2 meal preparation tasks with set-up and minimal prompting in order to engage in an essential daily living activity in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.
2. identify at least 3 topics of interest related to self-management in context of OT self-management group in order to promote active engagement in health management.

LTGs (by discharge): Corey will:

1. identify at least 2 specific coping skills he has learned to manage symptoms in order to promote active engagement in health management in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.
2. participate in at least 3 meal preparation tasks in OT Cooking Group with general supervision in order to engage in an essential daily living task in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.
3. identify 2 concrete steps he can take to increase social participation in order to strengthen support network upon returning to supported living in the community.
4. participate in Independent Medication Program for 4 days using environmental modifications in order to strengthen self-management skills in preparation for returning to supported living in the community.

Patient/Caregiver/Significant Other Actively Participated In Goal Setting: Yes

Response To Care: Patient aware of and agrees to general intervention plan

Education:

Services Provided:

Verbal Education: Received verbal education on role of OT services and objectives of OT group sessions.

Learning Demonstrated As Follows: Patient verbalizes understanding; May benefit from review.

Electronic Signatures:

Mathis, Diedre (OTR/L) (Signed 05/12/2020 15:47)

Authored: Evaluation Note, Subjective, Objective, Assessment, Plan, Education

Last Updated: 05/12/2020 15:47 by Mathis, Deidre (OTR/L)

Appendix 4: Abbreviations found in clinical documentation

These abbreviations were taken from the IPIR corpus used for developing annotations and include additional selected common abbreviations.

AA = Alcoholic Anonymous
ADHD = Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder
ADL = Activities of daily living
CRNP = Certified Registered Nurse Practitioner
c/w = consistent with
IADL – Instrumental activities of daily living
d/c = discharge
DV = domestic violence
DWI = Driving while intoxicated
dx = diagnosis, diagnosed
DME = Durable medical equipment
DORS = Division of Rehabilitation Services
DDA = Developmental Disabilities Administration
EtOH = Alcohol
f/u = follow up
GED = General education development
HI = Homicidal ideation
h/o or hx = history of
ICU = Intensive care unit
IV = intravenous
LE = Lower extremity or extremities
LGSW = Licensed graduate social worker
LCSW = Licensed social worker
LISW-CP = Licensed Independent social worker – clinical practice
MBA = Master of Business Administration
MH = mental health
MMSE or MSE = Mini mental status exam
MSW = Master of Social Work
OT = Occupational therapy or therapist
O2 = oxygen
PCP – Primary Care physician
PO or p.o. = by mouth
Psych = Psychology
PT = Physical therapy or therapist
Pt = patient
RVing – recreational vehicle[ing]
RN = Registered nurse
SLP = speech and Language pathologist

SOC = Social Security
SSA = Social Security Administration
SSD = Social Security Disability
SSDI = Social Security Disability Insurance
SSI = Social Security Insurance
SSRI = Selective Serotonin Reuptake Inhibitor
SI = Suicidal ideation
SO = significant other
s/p = status post
ST = Speech therapy or therapist
SW = social worker
TANF = Temporary Assistance for Needy Families
Tob = tobacco
Tx or Txt = treatment
VA == Veterans Administration
VNA = Visiting Nurse Association
Voc = vocational
w/ = with
w/c = wheelchair
w/o = without
yo or y/o = year old
x = times